

VITAMINE-A AND SESAME OIL IN VANASPATI (EDIBLE HYDROGENATED OIL)

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Two groups of samples, one vitaminised vanaspati and second corresponding vanaspati samples without vitamin-A, were stored at 40° and their Baudouin tests were carried out periodically for assaying the sesamol. The results show that the sesamol in samples without vitamin is stable to a remarkable extent, whereas vitamin-A fortified samples show a trend towards deterioration from the very first month. From the observations an inference can be drawn that vitamin-A and sesamol cannot exist together.

The India Government has made it compulsory to add minimum 5.0% raw or refined sesame oil and also vitamin-A to furnish a fortified product having a minimum potency of 300 I. U. per ounce for vitamin-A, and a minimum of 2.0R in Lovibond tintometer for sesame oil.

The form of vitamin-A supplied to Vanaspati (edible hydrogenated oil) factories in India is "Vanitin" brand synthetic vitamin-A acetate. As the vitamin-A acetate is a highly unsaturated compound, liable to oxidation and destruction, it can as well react with sesamol and destroy it during its own decomposition period.

The stability of vitamin-A in sesame oil and in margarine stock containing sesame oil has been studied¹. A study has also been made of the stability of sesamol in samples of vitaminised vanaspati.

EXPERIMENTAL

Samples were taken out from our 9-ton charge at 52°-55° just before adding vitamin for control samples and after adding vitamin for fortified samples. The average composition of the vanaspati had the following characteristics :

Cotton seed oil	...	...	10.0%
Refined sesame oil	...	...	7.0%
Groundnut oil	...	...	83.0%
Free fatty acid content	...	...	0.15%
Melting point	...	...	36-37°
Colour (Lovibond units)	...	...	0.7 Y and 0.2R.

Twentyfour samples were taken out for each batch of vanaspati, 12 control and 12 being fortified samples. Such 12 sets of samples were kept from 12 different batches during different periods.

Samples of each of the fortified portions and the corresponding controls were analysed for Baudouin test at the time of packing the batch in tins and after storage for 1, 2, 3 to 12 months. The vanaspati in the samples was melted to facilitate thorough mixing at 40° and the test was carried out as specified in V.O.P.C. specifications for the Baudouin test.

TABLE I
Samples without vitamin-A.

B. No.	At the time of packg.	After storage for (months).								
		1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.
1	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
16	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3
102	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
242	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
320	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0
341	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
591	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.2
603	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.8
663	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
693	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
705	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
735	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8

TABLE II
Samples with vitamin-A.

B. No.	I. U./oz added.	At the time of packg.	After storage (for months).								
			1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.
1	301.0	4.0	3.8	3.6	3.4	3.4	3.3	3.0	2.4	1.8	0.8
16	353.0	4.3	3.0	2.7	2.5	2.2	1.8	1.4	1.0	0.6	0.4
102	307.0	4.0	3.7	2.0	1.8	1.6	1.2	1.0	0.9	0.6	0.6
242	316.5	6.0	5.8	5.4	5.2	4.8	4.4	4.0	3.6	...	...
320	311.5	8.0	7.0	6.2	6.0	5.6	5.3	4.5	...	...	...
341	315.4	5.0	4.8	4.4	3.9	3.5	3.2	1.8	...	...	...
591	310.6	3.5	3.2	2.5	1.8	1.0	...	...	...	...	...
603	314.0	3.0	2.0	1.8	1.6	...	...	...	...	...	...
663	313.2	6.0	5.2	4.4	3.6	...	...	...	...	...	...
693	311.0	5.0	4.5	4.0	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
705	309.2	5.0	3.5	2.5	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
735	313.3	5.8	5.0	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

Examination of the data in Table I leads to the conclusion that sesamol content is stable in vanaspati samples for a period of 8 months and over.

Table II indicates that the sesamolín content shows a definite trend towards instability from the first month of storage, though slow in the beginning but to a marked degree in the later months, so much so that the Baudouin test reading is below the minimum specified of 2.0R.

In some cases where the initial Baudouin test reading is low *i.e.*, 3.0R, 3.5R at the packing time, it is destroyed within three months of storage.

The causes of the instability of sesamolín in presence of vitamin-A acetate are not known but it may be presumed that the vitamin-A acetate on keeping gradually hydrolyses to liberate acetic acid which may react with sesamolín and obliterate the Villavecchia test.

R E F E R E N C E

1. *J. Amer. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 329.